

Effects of Virtual and Mixed Reality Visual Stimuli on Center-of-Gravity Sway During Quiet Stance

Muhammad Shulhan Khairy, Yeoh Wen Liang, Osamu Fukuda

Abstract: Visual cues strongly influence postural control and fall risk, yet direct comparisons between Mixed Reality (MR) and Virtual Reality (VR) on center-of-gravity (CoG) sway are limited. This study investigated the effects of RE (real environment), MR, and VR on CoG responses during quiet stance using moving-light gaze guidance visual stimuli. Ten healthy adult participants completed 12 experimental tasks, it consists of 3 environments (RE, VR, MR) and 4 frequency conditions (no-light, low, medium, high frequency). MR produced largest CoG sway than RE and VR for both Total Track Length (mean Δ TTL: MR = 315.69 ± 288.92 mm; RE = 221.18 ± 280.15 mm; VR = 167.44 ± 177.86 mm, n = 30) and Trajectory Length per Unit (mean Δ Traj: MR = 2.59 ± 2.36 mm; RE = 1.79 ± 2.30 mm; VR = 1.38 ± 1.46 mm, n = 30). This study results show that MR tended to elicit greater sway, compared to RE and VR.

Keywords: balance control, body sway, postural stability, rehabilitation, virtual and mixed reality, visual stimuli.

I. INTRODUCTION

Falls are among the most common and critical health problems worldwide, with approximately 27% of older adults experiencing a fall each year [1]. An estimated 684,000 fatal falls occur annually [2]. Falls significantly reduce quality of life, often leading to immobility, fractures [3], deterioration of overall health, and loss of independence in daily activities [4]. Moreover, fatal falls are a leading contributor to mortality among older adults [5]. Risk factors for falls include impaired balance, gait problems, cognitive decline, and hazardous environments [6].

Human postural stability plays a central role in reducing fall risk. It relies on the integration of vestibular, proprioceptive, and visual sensory inputs to maintain the center of gravity (CoG) within the body's support base [7], [8]. Among these, visual inputs dominate spatial orientation and contribute more than 70% of balance regulation during standing [9]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that visual stimuli strongly influence body sway during quiet stance, as the nervous system responds to maintain balance [8], [10], [11], [12].

Given the crucial role of visual information in balance, immersive technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Mixed Reality (MR) are increasingly explored in rehabilitation and fall-prevention contexts. VR immerses users in a fully virtual environment, detached from the

real world, whereas MR overlays virtual elements onto the real environment, allowing simultaneous interaction with both [13]. Because VR alters the user's visual environment, it can manipulate balance perception and CoG sway, particularly during quiet stance conditions [14]. MR, by contrast, has been less studied, despite its potential to provide ecologically valid training or assessment scenarios that combine real-world grounding with controlled virtual stimuli.

Several studies have shown that VR-based visual stimuli affect postural stability. Imaizumi et al. [15] reported that wearing a VR headset with eyes open increased CoG sway compared to natural vision. Tashiro et al. [11], reported that visual tilt stimuli presented in VR significantly amplified body sway in both younger and older adults, with stronger effects at larger tilt angles. Similarly, other studies have revealed that the amplitude and frequency of VR visual perturbations influence sway responses [8], [10], [16]. Collectively, these findings confirm that VR can reliably alter postural control during quiet stance.

Although research on MR is more limited, initial findings suggest it also influences postural control. Muto et al. [17] reported reduced sway during walking tasks using MR, while Zhang et al. [18] found that MR-based reaching tasks increased postural demands compared to real environments. However, the relative effects of VR and MR on postural sway, particularly in quiet stance

Corresponding Author: Muhammad Shulhan Khairy. Graduate School of Science and Engineering, Saga University, Honjo Machi 1, Saga City, 840-8502, Japan. E-mail: shulhankhairy@gmail.com

conditions remain underexplored.

While VR has been widely studied as a tool to manipulate visual balance cues, there is little direct comparison with MR in terms of their effects on CoG sway during quiet stance. This creates two key research questions in this study, which are “Does MR influence postural stability differently than VR when both are used as visual stimuli?” and “Which of the two environments (VR or MR) induces greater or lesser sway under identical experimental conditions?”. This study addresses these gaps by directly comparing VR and MR in their effects on human CoG sway during quiet stance. Participants stood on a force plate while following sinusoidal moving light stimuli as gaze guidance under VR, MR, and real-environment (RE) conditions. We hypothesized that CoG sway in MR would be closer to RE, given its naturalistic integration of real and virtual cues, whereas VR would induce greater deviations due to the fully immersive and potentially unnatural visual context.

This study consists of introduction on chapter 1, describing the study background, related study, and study aim. Chapter 2 describes the method that we conduct in our study. Chapter 3 describes the results and discussions of experiments conducted. Chapter 4 describes the conclusions of this study.

II. METHODS

A. Participants

This study was conducted as a preliminary study in order to investigate the impact of VR and MR visual stimuli on human CoG sway comparatively. Ten healthy adult participants were involved (8 male and 2 females, mean \pm SD age: 30.8 ± 6.55 years, height: 164.7 ± 5.44 cm, and weight: 71.7 ± 12.88 kg) as shown on Table 1. None of the participants had a history of balance or vestibular disorders.

Table 1 Participants descriptive statistics

	Adult Participants (n=10)
Men	8 (80.0%)
Women (%)	2 (20.0%)
Age (years)	30.8 ± 6.55
Height (cm)	164.7 ± 5.44
Weight (kg)	71.7 ± 12.88

This study was conducted under the approval of Saga University Ethical Review Board (R4-38). All the participants were given the experiment purpose and method, and consent form was signed by each participant before the experiment conducted.

B. Experimental Setup

B-1. VR and MR Environment Setup

A head-mounted display (HMD) was used in this study, employing the Meta Quest 3 (Meta Inc., USA) to accommodate both VR and MR environments. The HMD provides a resolution of 2064×2208 pixels per eye with a refresh rate of 60 Hz. In VR mode, the HMD offers a fully immersive visual experience for participants. In contrast, in MR mode, the device operates in passthrough mode, allowing participants to interact simultaneously with the virtual visual stimuli and the real environment. Hand controllers were also utilized to provide task instructions through the HMD.

The software for the HMD was developed using Unity Engine (Unity Technologies, USA), version 2022.3.53f1, with several dependencies, including the Meta XR All-in-One SDK (version 77.0), which was used to implement the experimental environment.

B-2. Real Environment Setup

A microcontroller device was utilized in this study, which was Arduino MKR Wifi 1010 (Arduino, Italy) to give command to the actuator. The device was connected to 5V power, and LED strip WS2812B that utilized as visual stimuli in real environment.

Fig. 1. Participants' point of view (top). Experimental environment configuration (bottom)

Fig. 2. Example of gaze guidance of each environment

B-3. Center of Gravity (CoG) Measurement

Center of gravity (CoG) sway was measured using a force plate T.K.K 5810 (Takei Measuring Instruments Inc., Japan). The participants were standing above the force plate during experiment session; therefore, CoG sway data were gathered simultaneously. In order to ensure safety conditions, one assistant stood behind each participant during the experiment, as visual stimuli may induce postural instability or loss of balance in some individuals.

Force plate device was utilized to measure total trajectory track length (mm), trajectory length per unit time (mm/s), X-axis trajectory length (mm), Y-axis trajectory length (mm), peripheral area (mm²), and rectangular area (mm²). The total trajectory track length summarizes the CoG from both the X- and Y-axes. The trajectory length per unit time was employed to quantify movement speed, which total trajectory length divided by measurement time. The X-axis and Y-axis trajectory length indicates the horizontal and vertical distance covered. The peripheral area denotes the region defined by the outermost points. The rectangular area represents the space enclosed by trajectory's outer border [11]. Total trajectory track length (TTL) is referred to (1), meanwhile trajectory length per unit time (Traj) is referred to (2).

$$TTL = \sum \sqrt{(x_n - x_{n-1})^2 + (y_n - y_{n-1})^2} \quad (1)$$

$$Traj = \frac{\text{Total trajectory length (mm)}}{\text{Measurement time (s)}} \quad (2)$$

C. Experimental Procedure

C-1. Experimental Environment

This study utilizes three environmental experiments, which are real environment, VR environment, and MR environment. In real environmental conditions, the participants were obligated to stand above the force plate

and could see the real visual stimuli. VR and MR environment conditions were the same, which the participants should stand above the force plate. While in VR, the participants entered a fully virtual condition, see the virtual LED strip. Meanwhile, in MR environment conditions, the participants could see their real environment, simultaneously with virtual object of LED strip for visual stimuli. In all environments, the LED strip is attached to the wall, while two black strips are attached vertically as guidance for the participants recognizing their body orientation during the experiment. The real LED strip is shown in RE, while the virtual one is shown in VR and MR. The environment configuration can be seen on Fig. 1.

C-2. Experimental Flow and Tasks

Experimental tasks are conducted in three different environments, as mentioned before, which are real environment (RE), VR, and MR environment. Each environment was conducted separately. The participants should follow the gaze guidance as visual stimuli, which is a light that is shown from LED strip and move continuously following the sinusoidal wave pattern horizontally as shown on Fig. 2. The mechanism of gaze guidance following is quiet stance position above the force plate, then the participants' head should move (left to right, right to left repeatedly) based on the light movement, while the body position remains still. Participants position during experiment can be seen on Fig. 1.

Each experimental environment started with control condition, which is participants quiet stance position without gaze guidance as the baseline. After that, participants were faced with the gaze guidance, with three experimental conditions of frequency, which are low (0.1 Hz), medium (0.3 Hz), and high (0.5 Hz). Both

Fig. 3. Sample of participants' trajectory data across environments and frequencies (left: RE; middle: VR, right: MR)

experimental and control conditions are conducted in 2 minutes. During each interval between conditions, participants were required to rest for 5 minutes to minimize carry-over effects and physical fatigue that could influence CoG sway. These three experimental conditions sequences were conducted randomly by each participant, as were the experimental environment sequences. Each environment was conducted on a different day, to anticipate participants fatigue that probably influenced the next experiment.

D. Data Analysis

All the output measures were expressed as within-subject differences from the control condition to the baseline. For each participant i , environment e , and light frequency f , the delta for Total Track Length (TTL) and the delta for Trajectory Length per Unit was computed based on (3) and (4).

$$\Delta TTL_{i,e,f} = TTL_{i,e,f} - TTL_{i,e,no} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Traj_{i,e,f} = Traj_{i,e,f} - Traj_{i,e,no} \quad (4)$$

Group summary measures were obtained by averaging these deltas across participants and frequencies for each environment. The overall mean delta Total Track Length for environment e was calculated based on (5) and the overall mean delta Trajectory Length per Unit for environment e based on (6), where P denotes the number of participants, $F = \{\text{low, medium, high}\}$ denotes the set of stimulus frequencies, and N_e is the number of valid delta observations for environment e .

$$\overline{\Delta TTL}_e = \frac{1}{N_e} \sum_{i=1}^P \sum_{f \in F} \Delta TTL_{i,e,f} \quad (5)$$

$$\overline{\Delta Traj}_e = \frac{1}{N_e} \sum_{i=1}^P \sum_{f \in F} \Delta Traj_{i,e,f} \quad (6)$$

Summary calculation also gathered for each frequency, the mean delta per environment and frequency was calculated as (7) and (8) with $N_{e,f}$ denoting the number of participants with valid baseline and frequency measurements for the specific environment–frequency.

$$\overline{\Delta TTL}_{e,f} = \frac{1}{N_{e,f}} \sum_{i=1}^P \Delta TTL_{i,e,f} \quad (7)$$

$$\overline{\Delta Traj}_{e,f} = \frac{1}{N_{e,f}} \sum_{i=1}^P \Delta Traj_{i,e,f} \quad (8)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TTL data that gathered from force plate device were illustrated as shown on Fig. 3. Based on data that were gathered, mean TTL was 1015.34 ± 445.22 mm ($n = 40$) in MR, 945.84 ± 417.57 mm ($n = 40$) in RE, and 921.42 ± 344.71 mm ($n = 40$) in VR. Although MR exhibited the largest mean TTL numerically, the large within-group standard deviations produce substantial overlap among environments; the observed ranges (as reflected by SD) indicate that intersubject variability is large relative to the mean differences. This pattern motivates delta analysis to reduce between-subject baseline effects. Mean Trajectory Length per Unit resulted that MR = 8.32 ± 3.65 mm ($n = 40$), RE = 7.74 ± 3.42 mm ($n = 40$), and VR = 7.56 ± 2.84 mm ($n = 40$). MR shows a modestly larger mean trajectory, but SD values of around 3 mm indicate that participant-level

variability is comparable to or larger than these mean differences.

According to Fig. 4, in case of subtracting participant and environment variables with no-gaze guidance condition as the baseline, mean Δ TTL was MR = 315.69 \pm 288.92 mm (n = 30), RE = 221.18 \pm 280.15 mm (n = 30), and VR = 167.44 \pm 177.86 mm (n = 30). Numerically, MR produced a larger mean delta than RE (MR - RE \approx +94.51 mm) and VR (MR - VR \approx +148.25 mm). However, the SDs are large (\approx 178–289 mm), and the within-subject individual points shows heterogeneous responses. Mean Δ Traj were MR = 2.59 \pm 2.36 mm (n = 30), RE = 1.79 \pm 2.30 mm (n = 30), and VR = 1.38 \pm 1.46 mm (n = 30). MR mean Δ Traj is larger than RE by \approx 0.80 mm and larger than VR by \approx 1.21 mm. SDs are similar in magnitude to the means (SDs \approx 1.46–2.36 mm), indicating modest effect sizes relative to variability.

The breakdown by frequency (n = 10 for each frequency) reveals frequency-dependent differences within environments. The results (mean Δ TTL \pm SD, n = 10) are: MR-high = 432.92 \pm 360.65 mm, MR-medium = 340.20 \pm 273.94 mm, MR-low = 173.95 \pm 160.03 mm; RE-high = 308.47 \pm 299.18 mm, RE-medium = 171.52 \pm 299.82 mm, RE-low = 183.55 \pm 246.40 mm; VR-high = 164.77 \pm 148.97 mm, VR-medium = 132.14 \pm 136.75 mm, VR-low = 205.42 \pm 240.93 mm. Numerically, the largest mean Δ TTL occurs for MR-high (\approx 433 mm), substantially larger than all VR; nevertheless, SD in MR

(\approx 361 mm) is also large, so some participants drive the high mean. The frequency breakdown indicates that high frequency in MR and RE tends to produce larger mean Δ TTL than low or medium in those environments, while VR means are generally lower and less frequency-dependent.

Results for Δ Traj (mean \pm SD, n = 10) are: MR-high = 3.54 \pm 2.97 mm, MR-medium = 2.80 \pm 2.23 mm, MR-low = 1.42 \pm 1.30 mm; RE-high = 2.48 \pm 2.47 mm, RE-medium = 1.40 \pm 2.47 mm, RE-low = 1.49 \pm 2.00 mm; VR-high = 1.35 \pm 1.19 mm, VR-medium = 1.09 \pm 1.13 mm, VR-low = 1.70 \pm 1.99 mm. MR-high shows the largest mean Δ Traj (\approx 3.54 mm) while VR means remain close to \approx 1.1–1.7 mm. However, SDs are large relative to means for some data, indicating heterogeneity.

Overall, MR produced larger average delta responses than VR for both CoG metrics: mean Δ TTL was 315.69 \pm 288.92 mm for MR versus 167.44 \pm 177.86 mm for VR (n = 30 per environment), and mean Δ Traj was 2.59 \pm 2.36 mm for MR versus 1.38 \pm 1.46 mm for VR (n = 30). MR also produced larger average delta compared to RE for both CoG metrics: mean Δ TTL was 315.69 \pm 288.92 mm for MR versus 221.18 \pm 280.15 mm for RE (n = 30 per environment), and mean Δ Traj was 2.59 \pm 2.36 mm for MR versus 1.79 \pm 2.30 mm for RE (n = 30). MR elicited greater sway in both total track length and trajectory length per unit than RE and VR, particularly at high visual stimuli frequency.

Table 2 Numerical results of TTL, Traj, Δ TTL, and Δ Traj across environment

Environment	n = 40		n = 30	
	TTL [mm]	Traj [mm]	Δ TTL [mm]	Δ Traj [mm]
MR	1015.34 \pm 445.22	8.32 \pm 3.65	315.69 \pm 288.92	2.59 \pm 2.36
RE	945.84 \pm 417.57	7.74 \pm 3.42	221.18 \pm 280.15	1.79 \pm 2.30
VR	921.42 \pm 344.71	7.56 \pm 2.84	167.44 \pm 177.86	1.38 \pm 1.46

Table 3 Numerical results of Δ TTL, and Δ Traj across environment and frequency

Environment	Frequency (n=10)					
	High		Medium		Low	
	Δ TTL [mm]	Δ Traj [mm]	Δ TTL [mm]	Δ Traj [mm]	Δ TTL [mm]	Δ Traj [mm]
MR	432.92 \pm 360.65	3.54 \pm 2.97	340.20 \pm 273.94	2.80 \pm 2.23	173.95 \pm 160.03	1.42 \pm 1.30
RE	308.47 \pm 299.18	2.48 \pm 2.47	171.52 \pm 299.82	1.40 \pm 2.47	183.55 \pm 246.40	1.49 \pm 2.00
VR	164.77 \pm 148.97	1.35 \pm 1.19	132.14 \pm 136.75	1.09 \pm 1.13	205.42 \pm 240.93	1.70 \pm 1.99

Based on data gathered, as shown on Table 2 and 3, when no gaze guidance task was present or when the LED movement was at the low cycle, CoG trajectory did not differ meaningfully across RE, VR, and MR. This observation indicates that, in the absence of a salient

moving visual stimuli, participants' postural control remained dominated by baseline sensory integration and intrinsic sway variability, and that the mere presentation modality (RE, MR, or VR) did not by itself alter quiet-stance sway. However, when the LED tracking or

Fig. 4. Mean Δ TTL and Δ Traj by environment and across frequency and environment

gaze guidance task was conducted, higher visual stimuli cycle rates produced larger CoG sway across environments, consistent with well-known frequency-dependent gain in visually evoked postural responses. MR showed a progressive increase in sway amplitude from low to medium to high cycles, which high frequency condition produced the largest group mean deltas for both TTL and Traj. This pattern is consistent with the view that MR has strong correlation with the participant's retained real-world sensorimotor references, leading to pronounced CoG modulation at higher stimulus frequencies.

We argue that plausible mechanistic contributor to the larger MR CoG sway in this study is passthrough latency. Measured passthrough latencies for Quest 3 have been reported in independent benchmarks on around 30-40 milliseconds [19]. Even modest latency in a dynamic visual stimulus can produce temporal misalignment between head/eye motion and visual feedback, increasing sensory conflict and driving larger corrective postural responses. Further study using various HMD, for example, Microsoft HoloLens, may yield lower apparent scene latency, which could reduce such conflict and attenuate induced sway.

In the RE condition, increased CoG sway with tracking tasks is expected because natural visual pursuit and large eye/head excursions directly drive vestibulo-ocular and oculomotor reflexes that influence posture. For VR, the comparatively smaller deltas observed here may reflect geometric and viewing-distance differences (closer screen distance to eyes and constrained visual parallax), or reduced head/eye excursion during the task. Direct measurement of horizontal head rotation and eye movement across VR and RE would possibly be beneficial for further study.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we compared the effects of Real Environment (RE), Mixed Reality (MR), and Virtual Reality (VR) on center of gravity (CoG) sway during quiet stance using moving light stimuli. Descriptively, MR produced larger baseline subtracted responses than both RE and VR for both Total Track Length. These descriptive results do not meet the initial hypothesis that MR would more closely resemble RE; instead, MR tended to elicit greater sway, compared to RE and VR in this study. For future studies, we recommend reporting effect sizes (and confidence intervals), examining participant-level consistency, and considering additional

sway metrics (e.g., RMS sway, COP velocity) to strengthen inference and generalizability.

During no gaze guidance task was present (or when LED movement was at the low cycle), CoG sway did not differ meaningfully across RE, VR, and MR, indicating that baseline sensory integration dominated quiet stance sway. When the gaze guidance task was active, higher stimulus cycle rates produced larger CoG sway across environments, with MR showing a progressive increase from low to high and the largest group mean deltas at high frequency for both TTL and Traj. A plausible mechanistic contributor to the enhanced MR responses is passthrough latency, which can introduce temporal misalignment between head/eye motion and visual feedback and thereby amplify corrective postural responses. The larger RE responses reflect natural pursuit and head/eye excursions, while the smaller VR deltas may relate to viewing geometry (closer virtual screens, constrained parallax) or reduced head motion. Therefore, further study could be conducted to compare passthrough-mode results with another HMD. Another further study is head rotation recording (comparing VR and RE) to examine whether kinematic differences explain the environment dependent sway patterns.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Saunders *et al.*, "Risk Factors for Falls in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: An Umbrella Review," *J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc.*, vol. 26, no. 9, p. 105765, Sept. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.jamda.2025.105765.
- [2] The World Health Organization, "Falls," Falls. Accessed: July 03, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/news-room/factsheets/detail/falls>
- [3] N. Salari, N. Darvishi, M. Ahmadipناه, S. Shohaimi, and M. Mohammadi, "Global prevalence of falls in the older adults: a comprehensive systematic review and meta-analysis," *J. Orthop. Surg.*, vol. 17, no. 1, p. 334, June 2022, doi: 10.1186/s13018-022-03222-1.
- [4] Y. Zhou, Y. Chen, L. Jiang, X. Zhang, and L. Ni, "The development of a risk prediction model for fall in patients with low vision: Based on lasso regression," *Geriatr. Nur. (Lond.)*, vol. 64, p. 103408, July 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.gerinurse.2025.103408.
- [5] W. A. Alkeridy *et al.*, "Risk factors and locations of falls among older pilgrims during Hajj: Implications for targeted prevention," *J. Infect.*

- Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 10, p. 102874, Oct. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.jiph.2025.102874.
- [6] A. Kapan, M. Ristic, R. Felsing, A. Konrad, and T. Waldhoer, "Predictive Accuracy of the 3-m Backward Walk Test for Fall Risk in Older Adults," *J. Am. Med. Dir. Assoc.*, vol. 26, no. 9, p. 105580, Sept. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.jamda.2025.105580.
- [7] R. J. Peterka, "Sensorimotor Integration in Human Postural Control," *J. Neurophysiol.*, vol. 88, no. 3, pp. 1097–1118, Sept. 2002, doi: 10.1152/jn.2002.88.3.1097.
- [8] S. Şirvan Tongar and Ç. Yazici-Mutlu, "How virtual reality is impacting balance: An examination of postural stability," *J. Bodyw. Mov. Ther.*, vol. 38, pp. 81–85, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.jbmt.2024.01.034.
- [9] L. Assländer and R. J. Peterka, "Sensory reweighting dynamics following removal and addition of visual and proprioceptive cues," *J. Neurophysiol.*, vol. 116, no. 2, pp. 272–285, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1152/jn.01145.2015.
- [10] A. Mohebbi, P. Amiri, and R. E. Kearney, "Identification of human balance control responses to visual inputs using virtual reality," *J. Neurophysiol.*, vol. 127, no. 4, pp. 1159–1170, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1152/jn.00283.2021.
- [11] T. Tashiro *et al.*, "Adaptation of Postural Sway in a Standing Position during Tilted Video Viewing Using Virtual Reality: A Comparison between Younger and Older Adults," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 9, p. 2718, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.3390/s24092718.
- [12] C. G. C. Horlings, M. G. Carpenter, U. M. Küng, F. Honegger, B. Wiederhold, and J. H. J. Allum, "Influence of virtual reality on postural stability during movements of quiet stance," *Neurosci. Lett.*, vol. 451, no. 3, pp. 227–231, Feb. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2008.12.057.
- [13] E. Dubreucq, S. Barlocco De La Vega, J. Bouaoud, A.-L. Philippon, and P.-C. Thiebaud, "Impact of virtual, augmented or mixed reality in basic life support training: A scoping review," *Clin. Simul. Nurs.*, vol. 99, p. 101672, Feb. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.ecns.2024.101672.
- [14] S. V. G. Cobb, S. Nichols, A. Ramsey, and J. R. Wilson, "Virtual Reality-Induced Symptoms and Effects (VRISE)," *Presence Teleoperators Virtual Environ.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 169–186, Apr. 1999, doi: 10.1162/105474699566152.
- [15] L. F. I. Imaizumi *et al.*, "Virtual reality head-mounted goggles increase the body sway of young adults during standing posture," *Neurosci. Lett.*, vol. 737, p. 135333, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2020.135333.
- [16] N. S. Chowdhury, W. Luu, S. Palmisano, H. Ujike, and J. Kim, "Spatial presence depends on 'coupling' between body sway and visual motion presented on head-mounted displays (HMDs)," *Appl. Ergon.*, vol. 92, p. 103355, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.apergo.2021.103355.
- [17] Y. Muto *et al.*, "Walking Posture Correction Using Mixed Reality for Self Visualization," in *Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 14014, M. Kurosu and A. Hashizume, Eds., in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 14014, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2023, pp. 135–145. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-35572-1_10.
- [18] Y. Zhang, A. Matsumoto, C. Oshima, K. Sakamoto, T. Sugiyama, and N. Liang, "Standing postural control during an upper limb reaching task in a mixed reality condition: analysis of center of pressure and lower limb muscle activities," *Virtual Real.*, vol. 29, no. 3, p. 93, June 2025, doi: 10.1007/s10055-025-01167-4.
- [19] T. Björk, "A Benchmark comparison with OptoFidelity BUDDY Test System among HTC VIVE XR Elite, Meta Quest 3, Meta Quest Pro, and Apple Vision Pro," Optofidelity. Accessed: Sept. 28, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.optofidelity.com/insights/blogs/apple-vision-pro-benchmark-test-1-see-through-latency-photon-to-photon>